

Nitroso Complexes of Rhenium-ReBr₃(NO) and its Derivatives

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Isolation and properties of ReCl₃(NO) and its derivatives have been reported earlier¹⁻³. The present communication reports the isolation of the corresponding bromine derivatives.

The parent compound viz., ReBr₃(NO) can be prepared in two ways. It is formed on dissolution of Re(OH)₃(NO)⁴, prepared by the hydrolysis of ReCl₃(NO), in aqueous hydrobromic acid and evaporating the same. Alternatively this can be directly prepared by heating Silver hexabromorhenate (IV) in a current of dry NO₂-free nitric oxide and subsequent extraction of the solid with ethanol.

Refluxing of Re(OH)₃(NO) with excess of aqueous hydrobromic acid yields the acid H₂ReBr₅(NO) from which slightly soluble caesium salt can be precipitated by the addition of caesium bromide. Fairly soluble rubidium salt can be crystallised from a mixture of rubidium bromide and H₂ReBr₅(NO). 1:10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridylum salts can also be prepared as insoluble precipitates. The pyridinium salt (pyH)₂[ReBr₅(NO)] can be prepared by the action of pyridinium hydrobromide and H₂ReBr₅(NO). It can also be directly synthesised by heating (pyH)₂Re^{IV}Br₆ in nitric oxide.

All these compounds are red to brown in colour. They are extremely susceptible to hydrolysis and are stable in aqueous and ethanolic solutions only in presence of free hydrobromic acid. ReBr₃(NO) is also hygroscopic in nature and is therefore difficult to keep outside a desiccator. These are easily oxidised aerially in aqueous alkaline solution and the solution shows the presence to NO₂⁻ ion.

Analytical results of a few compounds are given below, the analysis being done by heating the compounds in hydrogen gas⁵.

Compounds	Found %				Required %			
	Re.	Br.	NO	Alkali metal	Re	Br	NO	alkali metal
1. Cs ₂ [ReBr ₅ (NO)]	20.1	45.3	3.4	30.4	21.1	45.3	3.4	30.1
2. Rb ₂ [ReBr ₅ (NO)]	22.5	48.1	3.9	21.5	23.7	50.8	3.8	21.7
3. (pyH) ₂ [ReBr ₅ (NO)]	23.8	52.6	—	—	24.0	51.3	—	—

1. B. K. Sen, P. Bandyopadhyay and P. B. Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 496.

2. B. K. Sen, P. Bandyopadhyay and P. B. Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 227.

3. D. K. Hait and P. Bandyopadhyay. Communicated.

4. Unpublished work.

5. D. K. Hait, Subha Rakshit and P. Bandyopadhyay. Communicated.

The analysis of the parent compound $\text{ReBr}_3(\text{NO})$ shows the ratio of Re : Br as 1 : 3.

Further work in the series is in progress and the details will be published later.

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